

Who Is Imam Mahdi, Prophesied In Other Religions, And From Holy Fatima lineage?

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Abstract

Purpose: In this article, we will discuss the narrations and prophecies that exist in Islam, both in Shia, Sunni and other religions regarding Imam Mahdi. This article also attempts to deal with Holy Fatima and her characteristics. Also, we will show that Imam Mahdi is mentioned not only in other religions but also in other books. Also, this research was conducted to answer and clarify three questions that stated in the Introduction section.

Methods: We performed our methods in 4 stages: Identifying studies, Selection of Studies, Collating Studies, Reporting results.

Results: According to Abrahamic religions, a person will reappear and establish fairness and justice with the help of God, who is called Imam Mahdi and based on the opinion of Christians, he is Christ. If the Shiites, may Allah help them in His obedience, had fulfilled their covenant with united hearts, then there would have been no delay in meeting the Promised Saviour.

Conclusion: The concept of Imam Mahdi is universal and cannot just be rejected. The appearance of Imam Mahdi will coincide with the coming back of Jesus Christ. Imam Mahdi, with the assistance of the Messiah, will ensure the completion and practical actualization of the mission of the Prophet Muhammad. The Hidden Imam wrote to Abu-Omar Ameri: The Prophet's daughter (Holy Fatima) is a nice model for me. We hope this article will take an important step in acquainting people with Imam Mahdi and Jesus Christ and paving the ground for their reappearance.

Keywords: Imam Mahdi, Holy Fatima, Prophecies, Quran, Islam, Traditions

1. Introduction

The end times are a major theme in theological and philosophical subjects. In addition, the end-time principles of different religions have a great influence on the political positions as well as to the cultural and social affairs of different societies [79]. Judgment Day is considered the common chapter of all religions. One of the most important features of this era is the arrival and appearance of the lifeline of the Judgment Day, which has a very special place in the religions of Islam and Christianity [78]. God, the Glorified One, always places a special person of the Ummah as a witness of their deeds and of all nations, to testify of the Ummah's performance in the Divine Court on the Day of Judgment [34]. The religion of Islam based on the declaration of Imam Ali and the other Imams of the household will rule the world [89]. Islamic narratives speak of the social maturity of people during the era of Advent. Traditional Sharia scholars and Muslim modernists tend to support this theory [31]. In the Quran, there are many verses about the ideal city [40].

According to geographical and other sources, in the past, Shiites lived in different regions of Islamic countries. It is taken for granted that the dispersal of Shiites to various cities and regions had a remarkable impact on the information of Shiite science and ideas, and developed several

scientific centers and led to striking developments in the scientific base and the thought of the Shiites [94].

1.1. Belief in the coming of a Savior

In the Quran and Hadith, many facts about Imam Mahdi can also be found in the narrative verses of the Quran and many similarities between Imam Mahdi and the Prophets can be found [1]. Belief in the coming of a Savior at the end of the world is a principle common to all divine religions. A majority of Muslim scholars, whether Shia or Sunni, give an obvious explanation of the quality of the advent of Imam Mahdi and his contemporary events [3]. In Islamic traditions, the promised Mahdi is a man of the lineage and the household of the Prophet, bearing the same name as the Prophet. [16]. The Shia is waiting for the Messiah during an absence, and they would do so by passing through various trials and difficult situations and paving the way for the advent [21]. The issue of the existence of the twelfth Imam of the Shia Imami has been discussed many times historically [91]. A caravan was organized from the city of Qom to Samerra in Iraq for the pilgrimage to the shrine of Imam Hassan Askari. These men from the caravan managed to visit Imam Mahdi [96]. Shia in historical eras since the Safavid era have held the ninth day of Rabiol Avval sacred because this day in history is the beginning of Imam Mahdi's Imamate. Imam Mahdi's father was martyred on the 8th of the same month [95]. Also, after the death of Imam Askari, the house was investigated and all his female slaves examined by the midwife. For two years, the secret agents of the caliph searched for the successor of Imam Askari, who was Imam Mahdi, until they lost all hope. The eleventh Imam was buried in his house in Samarra next to his noble father [82].

MEETING WITH IMAM MAHDI (A.T.F.S) – 10TH CENTURY

Muqaddas Ardebeli was an illustrious Shia scholar. It is well-known about him that whenever he used to encounter a difficult problem which he was unable to solve, he used to go to the tomb of Imam Ali (A.S.) and present his problem. Imam Ali (A.S.), invariably provided the solution.

One of the students of Allama Ardebeli who was following his teacher closely states: "It was near midnight when being tired of studying, I was strolling in the courtyard of the shrine of Ameerul Momineen Ali Ibne Abi Talib (A.S.). In the luminous night, when all the doors of the sanctum were locked, I saw a person coming towards the tomb of Ali (A.S.). For a moment, I thought that it was a thief who intended to commit a robbery. I followed him. But when he reached the main door, to my utter amazement, the door swung open and the padlock opened by itself in welcome. He continued to move towards the grave and whenever he neared a door, it opened by itself till he entered the sanctum of Ameerul Momineen (A.S.) in a grand manner. He stood there and saluted the Imam (A.S.). He received the reply to his salutations and commenced the conversation. When the dialogue ended, he emerged and headed towards the mosque of Kufa. I followed him in order to get to the bottom of the mystery. When he reached the mosque of Kufa, he entered the Mihrab (niche of prayers where the Imam stands) and began to converse with someone in a subdued voice. After the conversation was over, he came out of the mosque and walked back to Najaf al-Ashraf. It was almost dawn when he was near the gate of the twin city. Suddenly, I felt like sneezing and though I tried my best to suppress it, I could not. The person ahead of me turned around and came towards me. On a closer look, I recognized him to be my honorable teacher, the great scholar Ayatullah Muqaddas-e-Ardebeli.

After conveying my salaam to him, I said, "From the time, you entered the Holy Mausoleum till now, I have been following you. I beg to know with whom were you talking at the mausoleum of Imam Ali (A.S.) and the mosque of Kufa?"

Muqaddas Ardebeli first put me under an oath not to disclose this secret till he was alive. Then proceeded to tell me that whenever he came across a difficult problem in Islamic laws which he could not solve, he used to present this query to Imam Ali Ibne Abi Talib (A.S.) and obtain the solution for the same. Last night, Ali (A.S.) directed me to contact Hazrat Sahibuz Zamaan (A.S.) and said, "My son Mahdi (A.S.) is at the Mosque of Kufa. He is the Imam of your time. Go to him and seek the solution of your problem."

Obeying the order of Ali (A.S.), I went to the Kufa mosque and found Hazrat Sahibul Amr standing in the Mihrab. I presented my problem to my Master and received the solution.

(Al-Anwaar un-Nomaniya, Vol. 2, pg. 303)

Figure 1

1.2. Occultation Of Imam Mahdi

In the Shia hadith, the questioning and receipt of the Imam's answers is done in writing, usually transmitted by messengers. Ali Ebn Mahziar was a thoughtful scholar of hadith who collected and preserved several scriptures and passed them on to subsequent generations [7].

Regarding the occultation of Imam Mahdi, it has been noted that the Shiites did not specify in their reports a timetable for the appearance of the Imam [6]. In the great occultation of Imam Mahdi, it is still permissible to call him Muhammad unless there is a greater danger of doing so [30]. Uthman Ibn Sa'id was one of the main elements of the representative body established as the main agent of the Imamia during the life of Imam Askari and the beginning of the brief occultation. He was able to handle many important issues of that time, including financial matters, on the orders of the Imam, and he tried to resolve the issue raised with the occultation of the twelfth Imam through the guidance of the Imam Mahdi and using some of his agents to solve during Imam Askari's period [49].

If Muslims want to revive the civilization of the early centuries of Islam and achieve a civilization that fits the culture of Islam, Muslims have no other way than to initiate different kinds of science and produce knowledge [90]. Friday's prayer is important in the evolution of society and individuals. This verdict could be one of the best keys for the Cultural Revolution in Shiite society and for making evolution of a cultural, economic and political basis in any society [51]. One of the functions of "praying for the health of Imam Mahdi" is to be sought in the benefit given to the supplicant. Alternate prayer is considered a spiritual reason for the preservation of the imam [93].

Figure 2

<p>Britannica</p>	<p>Muḥammad al-Mahdī al-Ḥujjah, in full Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥasan ibn Alī al-Mahdī al-Ḥujjah, also called Muḥammad al-Muntazar, the Hidden Imam, or the Twelfth Imam, (Disappeared 878), 12th and last imam, venerated by the Ithnā Ashariyyah, or Twelver sect, the main body of Shīite Muslims. It is believed that Muḥammad al-Mahdī al-Ḥujjah has been concealed by God (a doctrine known as Ghaybah (Occultation)) and that he will reappear in time as the Mahdī, a messianic deliverer.¹</p> <p>While narrating the similarity of Imam Mahdi with the past Prophets, Imam Baqir states: In "differences concerning him", he is like Prophet Jesus. Some people might say that he is yet to be born, while some others might say that he was already born, but he died later, while some others may say that he was killed.²</p>
<p>A Special Feature Of The Generation Of Imam Mahdi</p>	<p>Abraham's race was divided into two children, Isaac and Ishmael. From the descendants of Isaac: Joseph, Moses, Aaron, David, Solomon and Jesus were born and from the descendants of Ishmael: Muhammad was born. In Judaism, descent goes from mother to child, and in Islam, descent goes from father to son. Imam Mahdi has a special feature; he reaches Prophet Muhammad and Ishmael from his father and the lineage of Jesus and Isaac from his mother, who was the daughter of the Roman king. Imam Mahdi is not only the Imam of the Shiites but also the Imam and Savior of all nations, the Imam of all human beings, and probably the title of "Son of man" in the Bible, is because you do not see race, but he is the representative and caliph of God.</p>

Table 4

1.3. The Prophet's Last Will and the Twelve Imams

The last will of the Prophet was to name his successors and many other things. The last will was to establish the Imamatus of twelve leaders, just like the twelve judges of the Israelites. Sunni's sources have also preserved much of the truth about the twelve imams and the hostile Umayyad campaign has failed to wipe it out of Islamic history and this is largely due to the opposition of Ahl Bayt's first imams, in particular of the Imams Ali, Imam Hassan and Imam Hussein [22].

¹ Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2019, March 15). Muḥammad al-Mahdī al-Ḥujjah. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Muhammad-al-Mahdi-al-Hujjah>

² Kamaluddin, page 327

The succession of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) is considered the point of distinction between the Shiites and the other Islamic sects. The main axis of the Shia faith is the belief that the successor of the Prophet Muhammad is chosen by the command of God and within the exclusive government of God, and the recognition of the twelve apostles called Imams is considered an essential element in the Shiites [23]. Ibn Mas'ud quoted several hadith of Prophet Muhammad, while some great Sunni narrators quoted about nine hundred narrations of Prophet Muhammad through him. One of these narrations is a valid hadith which mentions the twelve successors of the Prophet. In this hadith, the Prophet Muhammad gave the number of his successors and the rulers of the Islamic Ummah after him as twelve, comparing them to the rulers and chiefs of the tribes of the Children of Israel. The above hadith cannot be applied to anyone other than the Imams of the Prophet's descendants [48]. The Shiite interpretation of the Apocalypse of the Twelve gave it back its original meaning, the number 12 literally meaning twelve rulers who will successively govern the Muslims from the death of the Prophet until the Day of Judgment [85]. The word Shi'a literally means "follower" and comes from the expression "shi'at-u Ali" = a disciple of Imam Ali. The Shiites mainly apply it to the twelve successors of the Prophet, starting with Imam Ali and ending with Imam Mahdi [83].

1.4. Cyberspace - A New Generation of Social Relations

Globalization is one of the issues that plays a decisive role in the human economy. Cyberspace is a new generation of social relationships that has been able to open up in people's lives. The downside of Internet communication seems to be that communication in cyberspace is text-based. Therefore, it lacks visual and auditory cues in bidirectional interaction [15]. Cyberspace is a collection of information which, contrary to Western belief, is not free or freely accessible [14]. While the use of cyberspace can provide good educational opportunities in the religious education of educators, if left unattended, it can cause irreparable harm to educators and society [13].

This research was conducted to answer and clarify;

1. Who is Imam Mahdi, prophesied in other Religions?
2. Who is Holy Fatima?
3. How Imam Mahdi prophesied in other Religions books?

2. Methods

2.1. Identifying studies

We searched for articles on Google, PubMed, International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS), Google Scholar, SID (Scientific Information Database), Scopus, Atla Religion Database,

Web of Science with the search terms "Imam Mahdi", "Holy Fatima", "Quran", "Islam", "Traditions", "Prophesies". A search was also conducted using some universities relevant journal regarding our purposes to identify studies.

2.2. Selection of Studies

We reviewed and selected the relevant manuscript through reading and evaluating the title and abstracts of each study. With rigorous analysis, we omitted some irrelevant researches. Therefore, with this selection of manuscripts, we conducted a research paper.

2.3. Collating Studies

We also performed classifications to organize each datum, from manuscripts, to its relevant place to assess and evaluate.

2.4. Reporting results

Finally, with collecting and analyzing and performing our research purposes, we reported our findings. The figures were designed to improve the impact and validity of this research.

3. Results

3.1. Mahdism

Mahdism as one of the Islamic teachings has always been accepted by Islamic scholars [33]. An article should be an introduction to the method of some research based on the intellectual approaches that our Imams have followed to explain the theme of the Imamate and the facts of Mahdism [8]. Faith in Mahdism is an Islamic faith and has always been considered since the time of the prophet of Islam. In the traditions various terms and characteristics are mentioned for Mahdism and the person of Imam Mahdi; Traditions that say: Hazrat Mahdi is one of the children of the Prophet and Fatima and from Atrah, and he is absent. Hazrat Mahdi is one of the Ahlul Bayt of the Prophet and from his family; Jesus comes upon Hazrat Mahdi's arrival and prays behind him. With his coming, justice will spread over the earth [24]. The pioneering Shia reading of Promise Mahdism arose within the framework of belief in Imam Mahdi. During Imam Sadiq's Imamate, the political space opened up gave him the opportunity to express his belief in Mahdiism more clearly than in previous periods. Na'māni is a Shia scholar who narrated many narrations of Imam Sadiq. Based on this book, Imam Sadiq's approach could be divided into three sections: denial, affirmation and explanation. The denial approach shows the denial of the Promised Imam's approach in the era of Imam Sadiq, which is divided into individual and behavioral denial. The affirmative approach consists in proving the existence of Imam Mahdi, his Occultation and his coming awaiting. The explanatory approach includes: the introduction of Imam Mahdi, his occultation and the signs of his coming. This approach has led to the formation of a specific school of intellectual and faith on Mahdiism [25].

خَاشِعَةً أَبْصَارُهُمْ تَرْهُفُهُمْ ذُلٌّ ذَلِكَ الْيَوْمَ الَّذِي كَانُوا يُوعَدُونَ

**"With their eyes cast down, covered by disgrace. That is the day they have been promised!"
Imam Baqir (as) explained the above verse by saying, "The day" refers to the day of the rising of the
Qaem (as). [Taweel Al Ayat Al Zahirah page 701]**

Figure 3

Research shows that during the time of Imam Kazem and Imam Reza, the teachings on Mahdism included not only apocalyptic and Mahdist principles, but also instructions to educate the public and a kind of setting to avoid the deviations associated with Mahdism [32]. One of the issues in the field of Mahdism is the question of the behavior of Imam Mahdi towards the followers of other religions during the uprising [26]. Another issue related to Mahdism is the question of global justice and how to implement it, for which there are many rational and traditional reasons for the need to implement it. The existence of traditions showing the judgment of Imam Mahdi based on his inner spiritual knowledge in Shia sources proves a new method of judgment based on the complete knowledge of the infallible Imam [27]. Explaining the relationship between religion and politics in the imamat of Shia Mahdism is one of the concerns of Muslim scholars. The Quran and the traditions of the infallibles have provided guidelines for coordinating the right interaction of religion [19]. The attitude of Mahdism has different cultural, political and social dimensions. The explanation of Mahdavi's goals against the idea of the neutrality of the government in liberalism is one of the political questions for the drawing of Islamic utopia [88].

اعلموا ان الله يحيي الارض بعد موتها قد بينا لكم الايات لعلكم تعقلون

“Know that Allah revives the earth (even) after it has died...” Imam Baqir (as) explained the verse saying, Allah will “[revive] the earth” through the Qaem (as) after it will die through the disbelief of its inhabitants, and the disbelievers are the dead ones. (Kamaluddin volume 2 page 668)

Imam Baqir (as) said, “The death of the earth refers to the disbelief of its inhabitants, and the disbelievers are the dead ones. However, Allah will [revive] the earth’ through the Qaem (as) who will (rule) the earth with justice. Therefore, earth and its people will be revived after being dead (by their disbelief).” (Taweel Al Ayat Al Zahirah page 638)

هل ينظرون إلا الساعة أن تأتيهم بغتة وهم لا يشعرون

“Are they waiting (for anything) but the hour which will come upon them suddenly while they perceive not?”

Zorara bin Ayun said, I asked Imam Baqir (as) about the verse, “Are they waiting (for anything) but the hour which will come upon them suddenly?”

Imam (as) replied, It is “The hour” of the rising of the Qaem (as) which “will come upon them suddenly.” (Taweel Al Ayat Al Zahirah page 552)

Figure 4

3.2. Mahdaviyat Teachings - The Importance of Islamic Education

According to Quranic verses and Islamic traditions, unity and convergence are two important factors in organizing the community and achieving its goal. One of these foundations is the belief in Mahdaviyat and its fundamental and common components, such as the reappearance of Imam Mahdi, the expectation of him and their certainty, the names and attributes of Imam Mahdi, his relatives, global governance, spreading justice [20]. In Mahdaviyat traditions, appearance symptoms can have positive or negative functions. Positive functions can lead to promising hopes, eliminate ignorance and better recognize Imam Mahdi, and negative functions help us identify false uprisings and false claimants of the time [2]. An article shows how Messianic thought was planned and the quality of Imam Sadegh's Mahdavi teachings when the Umayyads lost power and the Abbasids came to power. The Mahdavi doctrines taught by the Imam at this point in history not only provide Islamic education and apocalyptic Mahdaviism, but also demonstrate the importance of education, that is, attention to the public [46]. The Mahdaviyyat teachings are one of the Islamic teachings subordinated to Shiites and Sunnis. Special Religious Sciences (Shafe'i and Hanafi), Sufi Tendencies and Orbital Wisdom are one of the major areas of

acceptance of Imam Mahdi's birth [18]. An article shows how the Messianic teachings of Imam Baqir developed and evaluates the quality of his Mahdavi teaching [47].

3.3. Sociological and historical studies

Sociological and historical studies argue that security at all times is a necessary requirement of every society. The righteous reign of Imam Mahdi that in some traditions, some symbols are explained for this arrangement. For example: quiet life of some predators with some animals [56]. The recent era is believed to have revived the flourishing of Imam Mahdi faith among the Zaidis, especially the Zaidan of Yemen [41]. The historical approach to discourse analysis is one of the methods for studying the Imami Hadith. Ibn Mahboub reflected on his Mahdism hadith in the face of four competing discourses that attempted to correct misconceptions about the promised genealogy, the appointment of Imam Mahdi, the lack of support from the Prophet Muhammad's family and the rising of the promised Savior in the intellectuals and the doctrine promotes the context of the society of the time [36].

وَالْعَصْرُ إِنَّ الْإِنْسَانَ لَفِي خُسْرٍ إِلَّا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَعَمِلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ وَتَوَّصُوا بِالْحَقِّ وَتَوَّصُوا بِالصَّبْرِ

“By the time, verily man is in loss, save those who believe, and do good deeds, and exhort one another to truth and exhort one another to endurance”

Mufazzal Ibne Umar said, I asked Imam Sadiq (as) about the words of Allah in the verse, “By the time, verily man is in loss”

Imam (as) replied, “The time” refers to the time of rising of the Qaem (as), and “man” refers to our enemies.

“Save those who believe” refers to those who believe in our signs.

“And do good deeds” refers to comforting the brothers.

“And exhort one another to truth” refers to the Imamate.

“And exhort one another to endurance” refers to the period of occultation. (Kamaluddin volume 2 page 656)

Figure 5

3.4. Gog and Magog - A Sign of Doom

Gog and Magog will come out at the end of the world as a sign of doom. A study aims to reveal

the reception of Sundanese in the story of Gog and Magog, which is represented by three Sundanese texts: Saifu Ad-Dharīb (SaD), Lajaj Dajal (LD) and Nawādirul 'Ulūm (NU). The SaD manuscripts state that they are found on Mount Qaf. SaD claimed to have 400,000 soldiers and each of them carried 1000 descendants. NU's manuscripts declare that all objects will be destroyed and humans will become their prey. The SaD's manuscript state that their death was due to strong winds; LD manuscripts claim they died from being attacked by thousands of mosquitoes, while NU manuscripts claim they died of disease. The SaD manuscript and the LD script both stated that Gog and Magog had been locked up by Dhul Qarnayn. Three texts give the same welcome of their majesty, when they emerge from the wall made by Dhul Qarnayn [11]. The other point we should clarify regarding Dhul Qarnayn is that Alexander the Great and Dhul Qarnayn are two different individuals [10].

Figure 6

3.5. Other studies

Ibn Zaki Al-Din declared the conquest of Jerusalem in the month of Rajab to Saladin, claiming to derive this prediction from Ibn Barrajan's commentary on the first verses of the Sura Ar-Rum. The basis of Ibn Barrajan's prediction is the contemplation of verses from the Quran. He believes that these verses herald the final victory of the Muslims with the advent of Imam Mahdi [9]. Imam Mahdi is one of the sons of Imam Ali (AS) and Ahlul Bayt (AS) and, as an Imam and divine Caliph, has the status of Welayat [39]. One issue for debate is whether it is permissible or

prohibited to publicly refer to Imam Mahdi's first and last name as Muhammad, which is one of the titles bestowed upon him. Among Islamic scholars, Mir Damad has declared it a sin to use this title, while another scholar, Sheikh Horr Ameli, takes the opposite view and defends the use of the title [5]. Research suggests that records of Imam Mahdi's martyrdom are inadequate. If we cannot prove martyrdom for convincing reasons, then the inevitable fate of Imam Mahdi's life is different from that of his fathers, for it was martyrdom, and was a natural death [4]. Muslims should pay attention to dissenting teachings and groups, which have always existed in the history of Islam, are emerging in the Islamic world [12].

Figure 7

3.6. Holy Fatima

Prophet Muhammad states that: “Fātima is a part of me”, adding that, “Whoever offends her offends me” [86]. The Hidden Imam (Imam Mahdi) wrote to Abu-Omar Ameri: "the Prophet's daughter (Holy Fatima) is a nice model for me". The following is part of what Hazrat-e Zahra did in defense of the velayat, i.e. the continuation of the course of prophethood: giving people reminders and warning them to cease being allegiance to the Caliph, resisting obligatory allegiance and supplication, reminding people of Ghadir-e Khom. One of the essential parts of their struggle is manifested in Fadak's sermon, as this land was considered an economic support for Hazrat-e Ali and the usurpation of Fadak belonging to Hazrat-e Zahra was considered illegitimate and contrary to the Quranic principles. A Point is a concrete example showing that the usurping Caliph did not deserve to be the successor of the Prophet [66]. The issue of

confiscated Fadak is one of the issues affecting political events and issues related to Islam. Fatima Zahra was deprived of her rights. According to the documentation available from the Fadak file, the decision of this government is contrary to the scriptures and tradition and the first caliph had no evidence that he claimed ownership and the judgment is wrong in several respects [67]. Fatima, in Fadak's famous sermon, defends her legal rights and, through her prominent speech, seeks to bring back to the right the people who had ignored the rights of the Prophet's family and his progeny [68]. A study decides to critically analyze Yusuf She'ar's attitude towards the question of the inheritance of the prophets based on the 16th verse of Sura an-Naml, as well as his interpretation of Fatimah Zahra's reference to that verse in the sermon by Fadakia. Unlike Shiite commentators who believe that the term inheritance in the above verse refers to property and rights, Yusuf She'ar attributes it to knowledge and prophecy and consequently interprets the reference to the above verse of Fatimah Zahra in Fadak's sermon in the presence of the companions of the Prophet as an accusation [69].

بَلِّ كَذِبُوا بِالسَّاعَةِ وَأَعْتَدْنَا لِمَنْ كَذَّبَ بِالسَّاعَةِ سَعِيرًا

“Nay, they belie the hour. We have prepared a blazing fire for him who belies the hour”

Imam Sadiq (as) said, There are twelve hours in a night. There are twelve hours in a day. There are twelve months (in a year). There are twelve Imams and the number of the chiefs (of Bani Israel) was twelve. Allah is one hour from the twelve hours, and this is the meaning of the words of Allah, “Nay, they belie the hour. We have prepared a blazing fire for him who belies the hour” (Chapter 25 verse 11). (Al Ghaybah by Nomani page 40)

Imam Sadiq (as) was questioned about the verse, “Nay, they belie the hour. We have prepared a blazing fire for him who belies the hour” (Chapter 25 verse 11).

Imam (as) replied, “Allah created twelve months in one year, twelve hours in the night, twelve hours in the day, and we (the Ahlul Bayt (as) are twelve narrators. The Commander of the Believers (as) is an hour from the twelve hours. (Al Ghaybah by Nomani page 40)

Insert Figure 8

3.7. Women's Dignity in Islam

Islam has declared duties corresponding to the dignity of women, to guarantee the dignity and identity of women and to reduce their inferiority to men, and thus provided the opportunity to realize their personal and behavioral independence. The Prophet's mission to eliminate the superstitions of the Arabs of the period of ignorance and to promote women to a high status was

concretized in his conduct towards Saint Fatimah [76]. At the time of the Prophet Muhammad, women enter the battlefield. The Prophet Muhammad permitted the presence of women in battle and commissioned troops of women to accompany him to war in order to provide nursing and medical assistance. The presence of women was due to their skills in the medical and health fields [77]. One study introduced pious women of Basra into the first two Islamic centuries and their knowledge, who specialized in the Qur'an and hadith [57].

فَإِذَا نَقَرَ فِي النَّاقُورِ فَذَلِكَ يَوْمٌ عَسِيرٌ عَلَى الْكَافِرِينَ غَيْرُ يَسِيرٍ

“when the trumpet is sounded, it will be a day of distress, not at all easy for the disbelievers”

Regarding the above verse, Imam Sadiq (as) said, There will be a victorious Imam from among us who will be hidden (from the eyes of the people). When Allah wills for him to reappear, He will send an inspiration to (the Qaem's) heart and he will rise with the order of Allah. (Al Kafi volume 1 page 343)

Imam Baqir (as) explained the verse, “For when the trumpet is sounded.” He (the Imam (as)) said, “The trumpet” refers to the announcement from the heavens which will announce, “Verily your Wali (master) is someone, son of someone. He is the Qaem (the rising Imam) who has come with the truth.”

This announcement will be made by Jibraeel three hours before the rising of the Qaem (as)

“It will be a day of distress, not at all easy for the disbelievers”. “The disbelievers” refer to the Murji’ah, who are those who disbelieved in the Grace of Allah and in the Wilayat of Ali bin Abi Talib (as). (Taweel Al Ayat Al Zahirah page 708)

Figure 9

3.8. Fatima is a perfect model

Studying the behavior of Hazrat-e Fatima and how she behaved under different conditions can give us hints in terms of spiritual insight [61]. There are many verses about Imam and Velayat in the Quran. It also contains many ideas about the house of the Prophet, especially Hazrat-e Zahra. The concepts associated with "Hazrat-e Sediqeh-e Kobra" are so profound that the term "Kosar" specifically refers to her [62]. Certain verses of the Quran were revealed to the holy Prophet's household. Hazrate Zahra, the daughter of the Prophet, is a member of the family of the Holy Prophet, according to the statement, "She belongs to the family of the Prophet", following the revelation of Tathir Verse (Ahzab, 33) [63]. Fatima Zahra is an admirable wife of Imam Ali; she is a perfect mother to her children, especially to Imam Hassan and Imam Hussein

and to her husband's nine children; a divine grace for the people of the past, the people of her time and those of generations to come; a guide for the men of her time and those of the future [64]. Hazrat-e Fatima is a perfect example of a believing individual, and her role could demonstrate the potential reach of the practice of religious injunctions and divine worship [65]. Fatima is a clear example of "divine purification" which enshrined religion and supported the immediate successor of the prophet [60].

3.9. Imam Ali, Husband of Holy Fatima

The nickname "AbuTraub" was an honor that Imam Ali received from the Prophet Muhammad for his devotion and piety and adoration [70]. After analyzing Imam Ali's narrative, the purpose of the article is to answer the question of what is a good model of a healthy diet based on Imam Ali's behavior? Eating less, eating quietly, dividing meals into several parts, observing individual hygiene and not talking while eating are among the principles of healthy eating recommended by Imam Ali. According to Imam Ali, eating soft foods such as nutrients, honey, vegetables and chicken should be preferred over hard foods. Having fruits like apples, pears and pomegranates cheers the heart and lifts the spirit [71]. The Alawite government is the model for establishing justice. Each of these dimensions includes important elements as stated in the words and deeds of Imam Ali [72]. In Nahj al-Balagha there are related dates which show the manner of Imam Ali to some extent. Imam Ali chose his attire and food considering factors such as imitation of the Prophet of God, empowerment from difficulties, austerity, avoidance of pride and selfishness, being a role model for others and most people, empathy for the needy and poor in society [73].

Figure 10

3.10. Ahl-Al-Bayt

With the unfortunate death of the Prophet, other tragic events happened to His Holy Household. The gathering of some Meccan emigrants and helpers of the Prophet at Saqifa caused the deviation on the way to the Caliphate, but there has been no significant research into the history and course of events leading to her Holiness Fatima (PBUH) (Sedighe Tahere) martyrdom [74]. The Prophet's family was formed from the presence of the Imams. The disappearance of Shia works as well as the sarcasm of opposition groups about small writings of Shias in the record of Shia culture have put Shias in an awkward position. Among these authors is Ibn Babaei Qomi, who has four separate writings on Saint Fatemeh [75]. Praise for Ahl-Al-Bayt and lamentations, for they are among the works that will revive the memories of these holy people. Ahl-Al-Bayt also praised their praises and described their virtues in this work [59]. One of the achievements of the realization of the Islamic-Iranian model of progress is the formation of an indigenous Islamic lifestyle [58]. Realizing the rule of Ahl Al-Bayt and living in its shadow are the main ambitions of the Shiites. So the Ahl Al-Bayt was asked to do it. Most of the narratives dealing with this subject state that no specific time has been set. Some narratives have mentioned the two tempos of 70 and 140 AH for this topic, the narrative mentioned in "Al-Kafi" [35].

4. Discussion

4.1. Quran verses and other references that refer to Imam Mahdi

There is an important common belief among all religions, which is faith and hope in the uprising of the Savior in apocalypse [80].

Concept Of Imam Mahdi In Hindu Holy Book

We read in the book "Didah": "after the destruction of the world, a king will appear in the End of Days who is the leader of all creatures, and his name is "Mansour" and conquers the entire world, and converts to his religion".

We also read from the Hindu Brahman scriptures: "..... the hand of God will appear and the last successor "Maitreya" will rise and conquer the east and the west of the world, and guide creatures".

Concept Of Imam Mahdi In Zoroastrian Book

In "Jamasp Namag" regarding the concept of Imam Mahdi that "A man will rise from the land of Arabs.... A man with a great head, great body and great legs and following the religion of his forefathers and with a great army, moves forward in Iran and constructs the lands and fills the earth with justice".

The concept of Imam Mahdi is universal and cannot just be rejected. The appearance of Imam Mahdi will coincide with the coming back of Jesus Christ. The appearance of Imam Mahdi is among the signs of the Day of Judgement. Imam Mahdi, with the assistance of the Messiah, will ensure the completion and practical actualization of the mission of the Prophet Muhammad [87].

Imam Mahdi In The Books Of Other Religions	
Buddahism The fifth Buddha Maitreya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zabur Manavi <p>The fifth Buddha and the last Buddha will come from the Land Buddhists to save all human beings. He is like a man who is ready to rise.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zabur Manavi <p>Life has been transformed so that the average life of people will be 80000 years. With these long lifetimes in the right field, a vertical chakra (guide) will come to teach the Buddha. He brings well-being and prosperity for people... when such a paradise is provided, Maitreya descends from Tushita.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zabur Manavi <p>Maitreya is riding a white camel and comes from the desert. Many of his companions, numbering more than 10000, accompany him. The corners of the city are filled with herbaceous trees. Trees whose fruits are magical fruits that symbolize a peaceful and productive environment... The land of joy and the emergence of the universe come true with all mercy, and mankind enters into the basic Dhamma of the last universal law. (Zabur Manavi, Albury)</p>
Judaism Qaem (Qa'im) Messiah	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Prophet Isaiah <p>He will judge the needy in justice, and will honestly rule for the oppressed of the earth. His belt will be fair and honest. The wolf will live with the lamb. (part 11, paragraphs, 1-10)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psalms Of David <p>The wicked are cut off, but those who trust in God, the humbled will be the heirs of the earth, will benefit from abundant health. The righteous will inherit the earth forever. (Old Testament, Psalms 37 P9-38)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psalms Of David <p>He will judge the people fairly. The sky rejoices and the earth exerts, the sea roars. The desert and everything in it is delighting. Then all the trees will sing because he comes. (Old Testament, Psalms 96)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daniel Prophesy <p>The great king who stands for the sons of your people is the Qa'im (Qaem). Many of them who are asleep will wake up, but for eternal life and their eternal shame and humiliation...Happy are those who wait. (page 1309, page 12, paragraph 1-12)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Prophet Habakkuk <p>Though he may delay, wait for him, since he will certainly come and delay, but he will gather all the nations together. (Chapter 2, paragraph 3-14)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Prophet Isaiah

	<p>He has to be the one who takes care of others. The doors will open. Cities will be welcomed first. The people of the universe will find peace in it. He is a man whom God has chosen and directed to conquer victory after victory and fulfill his real mission. (part 45)</p>
<p>Christianity The last Mahmid Son Of Man</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Gospel of Luke You should be like those who are waiting for their mistress to come back from wedding, so whenever he comes and knocks on the door, he immediately opens the door for him...so you also be ready because at a time when you do not think the Son Of Man comes. (page 116, part 12, paragraphs 35-40) • The Gospel of Matthew See the Son Of Man coming upon the clouds of heaven with great power...but no one knows of that day and hour ... at an hour you do not think the Son of Man is coming... (page 41, part24, paragraphs 1-37) • The Gospel of Mark Many will come in my name, claiming, 'I am he,' and will deceive many. (page 77, part13, paragraphs 1-9) • The Gospel Of John And he has given him authority to judge because he is the Son of Man. Do not be amazed at this, for a time is coming when all who are in their graves will hear his voice and come out. (page 152, part 5, paragraphs 26-28) • Epistle of Paul One who will arise to rule over the nations; in him the Gentiles will hope. (Page 261, part 15, Section 12) Then he (Jesus) left the crowds and went into the house. And his disciples approached him, saying, Explain to us the parable of the weeds of the field. He answered, The one who sows the good seed is the Son of Man.³
<p>Zoroastrianism Saoshyant Bahram</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avesta From the children of the daughter of that prophet, who is called the Sun of the World and the King of women, someone will become king in the world, according to the commandment of Yazata, who will be the last successor to the Prophet, in the middle of the world that is Mecca... many of the blessed and prophets will become alive. (part of Gathas, P8 and P9) • Jamasp Nameh In the Saoshyant period, all the two-legged and the four-legged demons are destroyed. All the ugliness and lies created by the devil will vanish. Sickness, old age, death, persecution, cruelty, heresy, and all the evils are gone... all people will live happily together. (Dēnkard, Sanjana, Volume 7-10:3) • Jamasp Nameh The Arab Prophet was the last messenger who will appear from the mountains of Mecca. The descendants of the personal Prophet will appear in Mecca, the successors of which are the Prophet and his ancestors. From his justice the wolf eats with the ewes and all the worlds will follow Muhammad's seal of worship. (Suitable letter, Mumbai: pages 121 and 122) • Zand in Hooman Yassen Saoshyant (the great savior of the world) will destroy poverty... make the people of the world both think, speak and act. That is why it will be called Saoshyant, which benefits the whole material world. (Avesta Farvardin Yasht P129)

Table 1

³ Matthew 13.36 and 13.37

Shiite scholars have no doubt that Imam Mahdi's father is Imam Hassan Askari. And on this subject, some Sunni scholars agree with Shiite scholars [52]. Imam Mahdi, is a character who will appear at the end of time and is awaited by his people. The concept of Imam Mahdi, according to the interpretation of the Shia Imamiyah, is that there are 3 roles of Imam Mahdi at the end of time which are mentioned in the verses of the Quran: 1. Imam Mahdi as heir and world leader, 2. Imam Mahdi as Strengthening Religion in the End Times 3. Imam Mahdi as a Witness for his Ummah [84].

The Quran has alluded to Imam Mahdi in various forms. Based on many Quranic and traditional reasons, many characteristics of Imam Mahdi and his presence are described in the narrative verses of the Quran [28]. Many first-hand accounts from Shia sources and some Sunni have mentioned the apparent age of Imam Mahdi at the time of Appearance [29]. The period of the appearance of Imam Mahdi is the time of the final realization of the creation of mankind on earth given in the Quran. The number of Quranic verses concerning Imam Mahdi and the future of the world is greater than the cases that the traditions declare to be directly related to Imam Mahdi [17]. Believing in the return of Imam Mahdi is an Islamic faith that occupies an excellent position in the Shiite school. It can be said that the main evidence behind this position is that the Shiites accepted his birth and his life [45]. The verse of "Estekhlaf" (Noor: 55) is one of the Quranic verses that some Sunni scholars have tried to discuss on the question of the Caliphate after the death of the Prophet Muhammad. It is one of their debates to prove the legitimacy of the Abu Bakr caliphate and the other caliphs. Sunni's scholars interpret the content of this verse in such a way that it can only be applied to the caliphs, and also reject any other interpretation. Some Sunni scholars such as Fakhr al-Razi have disputed the application of the ayah to Shia imams. Aloosi also ruled out his candidacy for Imam Mahdi. Based on Shia Hadith, the content and form of this verse indicate that the promised people are the twelve holy Imams, including Imam Mahdi and his followers [53].

﴿۞ نُوَكِّرُ شَمْلًا مَرَكُوْلُوْا بِمَلَكِن يَدَّلَاۤ اٰۤىۤءُ مَرۡعٰطِيۡلًا وَّحٰطَا نِيۡدُوْا وَّذٰهٰلِاِبۡ مَلُوۡسَرۡ لَسِرَاۤ اٰۤىۤدِلَا وُهٗ

Meaning: "It is He who sent His Messenger with guidance and the religion of truth, that He may make it prevail over all religions, even though the polytheists may detest it."

Imam Sadiq described the verse by stating: I swear to Allah that the Taweel (hidden interpretation) of this verse does not apply yet, and it will not apply until the rising of the Qaem (Imam Mahdi). When the Qaem (Imam Mahdi) rises, there will not remain any disbeliever in Allah nor any polytheist in Imamate who will not "detest" the rising of the Qaem (Imam Mahdi). (Even) if the disbelievers or the polytheists hide inside the rocks, the rocks will speak to the companions of the Qaem (Imam Mahdi) and say: "O believer! There is a disbeliever hiding inside of me, so break me and kill him."⁵

⁴ Surah Tawbah, 9:33

⁵ (Kamaluddin volume 2 page 670)

Imam Baqir declared: The (above verse) will apply at the time of the rising of Mahdi from the family of Muhammad, when everyone will believe in Muhammad.⁶

لَا يَلْقَى إِلَّا إِيَّاهُمْ أَوْ بِرَسُولِهِمْ فَفَزِعَ مَنْ دَغَا نَمَلًا لِيَوْمِ الْيَوْمِ لَا يَمُوتُ يَوْمَئِذٍ سِوَى الْيَوْمِ الَّذِي تُولَدُونَ وَتَوَلَّوْا لَصَّةَ أَمْلَقِ
 اللَّهُ نَذِيرًا مَن يَكْفُرْ تَبْلُغْ تَبْلُغْ تَبْلُغْ تَبْلُغْ نَمِمْ مَكْرَ اللَّهِ وَقَلَامُ مَهْدِيَّانِ وَنُظْمِ نَذِيرًا لَأَقْدَمِ دُونَ جَوِّ تَوَلَّوْا لَصَّةَ أَمْلَقِ مَهْدِيَّانِ
 نَذِيرًا بِأَصْلِهِ عَمَّا أَلَمَّ

Meaning: "So when Talut departed with the forces, he said: Surely Allah will try you with a river; whoever then drinks from it, he is not of me, and whoever does not taste of it, he is surely of me, except he who takes with his hand as much of it as fills the hand; but except a few of them they drank from it. So when he had crossed it, he and those who believed in him, said: We have today no power against Jalut and his forces. Those who were sure that they would meet their Lord said: How often has a small party vanquished a numerous host by Allah's permission, and Allah is with the patient."

Abu Baseer narrates, Imam Jafar Sadiq stated: "The companions of Talut were tested by a river and the companions of Imam Mahdi will be tested similarly."⁸

نَذِيرًا بِأَصْلِهِ رَشِيْبًا يَتَارِكُ مَثَلًا وَسُفْلًا أَوْ لَأَوْ مَلَأْنَا نَمِمْ صِفْوً عَوْجَلًا وَفَوْحَلًا نَمِمْ عِيَّ شِدِّمْ كُنُوْا لِبَنُوْ

Meaning: "And we will most certainly try you with somewhat, of fear and hunger, and loss of property and lives and fruits; and give good news to the patient."

Abu Baseer narrates from Imam Jafar Sadiq about this verse of Quran, Imam stated: "The year before Imam Mahdi reappears the following will happen; people will experience hunger; people will live in extreme fear of being killed; and people will suffer loss of wealth, life and livelihood. This saying of Allah clearly explains this."¹⁰

لَا يَكْفُرْ مَلَأْنَا يَأْتُوا لَوْ سُرُّوا أَوْ عِيْطُوا أَوْ لَأَوْ مَلَأْنَا نَمِمْ صِفْوً عَوْجَلًا وَفَوْحَلًا نَمِمْ عِيَّ شِدِّمْ كُنُوْا لِبَنُوْ

Meaning: "O you who believe! Obey Allah, and obey the Messenger and those vested with authority (by Allah) from among you."

Jabir bin Abdullah Al-Ansari stated: When the verse, O you who believe! Obey Allah, and obey the Messenger, and those vested with authority (by Allah) from among you are revealed. I asked the Messenger of Allah, O Messenger of Allah! We understood Allah and His Messenger, but who are "those vested with authority (by Allah)" whose obedience Allah has paired with your obedience?

The Prophet answered, O Jabir! They are my caliphs, and they are the Imams of the Muslims after me. The first one is Ali bin Abi Talib; after him, Hassan is the Imam; after him, Hussein; then Ali bin Hussein; then Muhammad bin Ali, who is known in the Torah as Baqir. And you, O Jabir, will meet him. So when you do, convey my salaam to him. After Muhammad bin Ali, it is the truthful, Jafar bin Muhammad; then Musa bin Jaafar; then Ali bin Musa; then Muhammad bin Ali; then Ali bin Muhammad; and then Hassan bin Ali. After him, it will be the one who bears the same name and title as mine. He is Allah's Decisive Proof on His land, and he is the Remainder of Allah in His creation. He was the son of Hasan bin Ali. Allah will achieve victory throughout His land through him. He is the one who will disappear from his Shia and his lovers for (a period of time) during which only those whose hearts Allah has tested, will stay steady in believing in his Imamat.

I (Jabir Al-Ansari) asked, "O Messenger of Allah! Will the Shia benefit from him when he is in Occultation?"

⁶ (Tafseer Majmaul Bayan volume 5 page 25; Tafseer Ayyashi volume 2 page 86; Tafseer Al Qummi volume 1 page 289)

⁷ Surah Baqarah, 2:249

⁸ (Al Ghaybah by Nomani page 316)

⁹ Surah Baqarah, 2:155

¹⁰ (Al Ghaybah by Nomani page 132)

¹¹ Surah Nisa, 4:59

The Prophet replied, "Yes! I swear to He who sent me as a prophet, that they will. They will see with his light and benefit from his Wilayat just like people benefit from the sun when it is behind the clouds. O Jabir! This is one of the secrets of Allah, which is contained in His knowledge. Do not share it except with the right people.¹²

دَعَبَ نَمَّ مَهْدَلْبِيلُو مَهْدِي صَنَزَا يَدَلَّا مَهْنِيد مَهْدِي نَكْمِيلُو مَهْلَبِي نَم نِيدَلَّا فَالْحَتْسَا امك ضِرْ لَا يَا مَهْدِي فَالْحَتْسَا يَا اِحْلا صِلَا اولِمَعُو مَكْنِم اوتَمَا نِيدَلَّا اَلله دَعُو
¹³ نَوْسَافَلَّا مَهْدِي كَلْبُو اَهْ كَلْبُو دَعَب رَفَك نَمُو اَنْبِيَشِي دِي نَوَكْرَتْسِي لَا يَنْتَوُدْبَعِي اَنْمَأ مَهْفُو د

Meaning: "Allah has promised to appoint those of you who believe and do good deeds, successors on earth, as He has appointed those before them, and He shall certainly establish their religion which He has chosen for them, and He will give them in exchange security after their fear. They shall worship Me and not associate anyone with Me."

Imam Sadiq described the above verse as follows: "This verse was revealed about the Qaem (Imam Mahdi) and his companions."¹⁴

In reply to a question about the above verse, Imam Sajjad declared: I swear to Allah that this (verse) refers to our Shia. Allah will make them (the successors, and He will replace their fear with security) through a man from us, the Ahlul Bayt. He is the Mahdi of this nation, and he is the one about whom the Messenger of Allah stated: Even if only one day remains from the life of this world, Allah will extend that day long enough for a man from my family, who bears the same name as mine, to rise. He will fill the earth with justice and equity, just as it will be filled with oppression and inequity.¹⁵

¹⁶ نَبِيْمُو مَهْدِي نَا مَكْلَرِي اَلله مَهْدِي

Meaning: "The remnant of Allah (Baqiyatullah) is better for you if you are believers."

Imam Jafar Sadiq stated: Our Qaem (Imam Mahdi) will gain the upper hand through his personality and he will be helped by Allah. The earth will contract for him and will reveal all her treasures at his disposal. Allah will make His religion triumph over all other religions in his hands, even though the polytheists might be averse to it. His empire will extend from East to West and will civilize all the destroyed nations. Prophet Jesus, the spirit of Allah will descend and pray behind him.

A person asked the Imam about the time of his advent. To this, the Imam narrated the signs of advent thus: The time when men will resemble women and women will resemble men, an increase in homosexuals and lesbians, women will drive vehicles, wrong testimonies will be accepted and justice thrown aside, people will consider murder, fornication, bribes and usury as some-thing usual, pious ones will be subjugated by evil ones, Sufyani will rise from Syria and Yemani from Yemen. Earth will be submerged at a place called Bayza. A person from the progeny of the Holy Prophet, whose name will be Ahmed bin Hasan alias Nafse Zakiyyah, will be martyred between Hajre Aswad and Maqame Ibrahim.

A voice will come from the sky stating that the truth is with Ali and his Shiahs. When the Imam reappears, his back will be towards Kabah and will be accompanied by 313 followers, commencing the crusade against injustice with the ayat of the Quran – "The remnant of Allah (Baqiyatullah), is good for you if you are amongst the believers." (Chapter 11 verse 86)

Afterwards, he will proclaim that he is the last Proof of Allah upon them and His Caliph in their midst. People will salute him thus. Peace be upon you, O Remnant of Allah on this earth. When 4,000 people gather around him, he will march from Mecca and prohibit worship of any other God except Allah. This will occur after a long Occultation. The same tradition is also narrated by Imam Muhammed Baqir. (Isbatul Rajat)

Table 2

¹² (Kamaluddin volume 1 page 253)

¹³ Surah Nur, 24:55

¹⁴ (Al Ghaybah by Nomani page 126)

¹⁵ (Tafseer Ayyashi volume 3 page 136)

¹⁶ Surah Hud, 11:86

<p>Imam Mahdi In Other Religions And Nations</p>	<p>As we have said, there are a number of people on the pretext that Imam Mahdi is not mentioned in the books of other religions, so such a person is not a savior. In the following, we will show that Imam Mahdi is not only mentioned in other religions but also in other books too.</p> <p>1) Kitab us Zind, the religious book of the Parsis, stated about the end of Injustice and the victory of the righteous as follows: "There is a constant conflict between the armies of Ahreman and Yazdan for supremacy in the land. Though mostly Ahreman is victorious, Yazdan is never fully vanquished, such that neither he nor his progeny remain. In difficulties, he receives help from God (Avarmazd) as he is His son. Thus, their war will go on for 9000 years until finally Yazdan receives a great victory. Ahreman's army will be defeated and no trace of his followers will remain in the heavens and the earth. Following the complete defeat of Ahreman and the conclusive victory of Yazdan, the world will progress towards perfection and happiness. Men will enjoy lasting peace and victory."¹⁷</p> <p>In the book Jamsabnaamah it is stated that: "In the land of Taziyaan, from the progeny of Bani Hashim, a person will rise. He will have a large head, a husky voice, and long shins. He will follow the religion of his ancestors. He will come to Persia with a big army. He will enliven the land with justice and equity."</p> <p>2) Shakmuni is considered as an intellectual in Indian Mythology. He explains the spiritual leader of humanity thus: In those days there will be a religion (All worldly authority will terminate in the hands of the son of the leader of the two worlds, Jamnad Kishan). The mountains of the east and the west will be under his authority. He will travel in the clouds. The angels would be his servants. Men and Jinn, all will submit to him. His rule will spread throughout the lands of the east and the west, and even beyond the oceans. There will be only one divine religion. Divine religion will be enlivened and everyone will believe and have recognition of only one God.¹⁸</p> <p>The Vedas, which are considered as the divine books of the Hindus, record thus: After the world suffers heavy destruction, a King will appear in the Last Age. He will be called "the Helped One" and will be a Universal Leader. He will rule the entire world and will collect all people into one religion. He will recognize every person from the believers as well as the disbelievers. He will be the one who actualizes God's will.</p>
<p>Imam Mahdi In The New Testament And Old Testament</p>	<p>Jesus says : the one who sowed the good seed is the Son Of Man. So the Son Of Man is someone else.</p> <p>In the Old Testament, it is stated that: "Let your waist be girded and your lamps burn. Be like men watching for their lord, when he returns from the marriage feast; that, when he comes and knocks, they may immediately open to him. Blessed are those servants, whom the lord will find watching when he comes..... Therefore, be ready also, for the Son of Man is coming in an hour that you don't expect him." (Luke 12:35-36)</p> <p>In the Old Testament, the divine book of the Jews, it is stated that; "A shoot will come up from the stump of Jesse; from his roots a branch will bear fruit. The Spirit of the LORD will rest on him..... with righteousness he will judge the needy, with justice he will give decisions for the poor of the earth. The wolf will live with the lamb, the leopard will lie down with the goat, the calf and the lion and the yearling together; and a little child will lead them. The cow will feed the bear, their</p>

¹⁷ Al-Fusul Al-Muhimmah, Ibn Sabbagh Maliki, p. 294

¹⁸ Religions and Mahdawiyyah, Muhammad Behisti, p. 18

	<p>young will lie down together, and the lion will eat straw like the ox. The infant will play near the lair of the cobra and put his hand into it. They will neither harm nor destroy all my holy mountains, for the earth will be full of the knowledge of the LORD as the waters cover the sea.” (Isaiah 11:1-10)</p> <p>There have been some speeches about him in various Gospels: “For as the lightning comes from the east and shines as far as the west, so will be the coming of the Son of Man...Then will appear in heaven the sign of the Son of Man, and then all the tribes of the earth will mourn, and they will see the Son of Man coming on the clouds of heaven with power and great glory.” (Matthew 24: 27, 30)</p> <p>And the same Gospel talks about ‘expectation’: “Therefore you also must be ready, for the Son of Man is coming at an hour you did not expect.” (Matthew 24: 44)</p> <p>And the Gospel of Mark talks about the responsibilities of those awaiting the savior: But concerning that day and hour no one knows, not even the angels of heaven, nor the Son, but the Father only. Be on guard, keep awake. Because you do not know when the time will come. (Mark 13:32, 33)</p> <p>An interesting point regarding the Gospels: “According to American Max in the “Lexicon of the Holy Bible”, the word ‘Son of Man’ is repeated 80 times in the Gospels and accessories (New Testament), of which 30 are adaptable to Jesus Christ and the other 50 are descriptions of the Savior who will come in apocalypse; And Jesus Christ will come with him and glorify him, and no one knows the date and time of his coming but great God.”</p> <p>5) In the Psalms, it is mentioned that: “For evil men will be cut off, but those who hope in the LORD will inherit the land. A little while, and the wicked will be no more; though you look for them, they will not be found. But the meek will inherit the land and enjoy great peace.” (Psalm 37: 9-12)</p> <p>In 35 out of the 150 parts of psalms, the coming of the Savior (The Psalms of David) is mentioned.</p>
<p>Imam Ali And Imam Mahdi In Hindu Scriptures</p>	<p>It is written in the "book of patecul" about the Apocalypse: When the day ends, the old world becomes new and the lord of the new kingdom appears from the descendants of the great leader of the world. One of them is the "honor of the End of Days" and the other one is the "greater honest" i.e. the great successor, whose name is "Pashan" and the name of that new lord is the "guide", he becomes the king rightfully, and he is the successor of "Rama" and he rules and has many miracles... His rule will last for a long time and his lifetime is the longest among descendants of the "greater honor" and the world ends with him. The aim of the "honor of the End of Days" is the great divine honor, i.e. Prophet Muhammad. "Pashan" is Imam Ali's Indian name. The "guide" is the sacred name of Imam Mahdi. In Sanskrit, "Rama" is the name of Allah.¹⁹</p>
<p>Imam Mahdi In Indian Holy Books</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In "Basque", one of the holy books of Indians: “The two worlds shall end with a just king in the apocalypse who is the leader of angels and mankind, and truth and rightfulness will be with him...and he will gain what is hidden in the seas and lands and sky.” • In "Shakmoni", an accredited Hindu book, it has been mentioned that: “Monarchy in this world will end by the son of the best creature, Koshen; (name of Prophet Muhammad. He will rule from the mountains of the east to west and will ride upon the clouds...” • Besides, we read in "Vashen-Jool" about the end of the world: “Eventually, the world will turn toward the one whose name is "Auspicious", he loves God and is one of God's special servants.”

¹⁹ The Savior in religions, Rouhollah Shakeri, p.226

<p>Imam Mahdi In The Zoroastrian Holy Books</p>	<p>The book of Jamasb Nameh, by Jamasb (one of the Zoroastrian scholars), describes the characteristics of Imam Mahdi as such, "A man with a large head, body and arms will come from the Tazian (Arabs) Land, of Hashem. He with the religion of his ancestors; he will come towards Iran with many troops; he shall civilize and fill the earth with justice such that the wolves and the sheep shall drink water together, the population shall increase and people shall live long lives once again, some men shall have fifty sons and daughters. The hills and valleys will become full of people and animals. It shall be like a wedding and all people shall again follow the religion of "Mehr Azmay" (Prophet Muhammad). Tyranny and rebellion will be a thing of the past, such that people shall forget how to bear arms. If I describe the goodness of this period, our lives will become so bitter."</p> <p>And somewhere else he says, "From the (last) prophet's descendants, someone will come to Medina who is the successor of the prophet, who follows his ancestor's religion. From the justice he practices, the wolves and the sheep shall drink water together; the entire world will become "Mehr Azmay" (Prophet Muhammad's (PBUH&HP)) followers."</p> <p>In the book of Zand and HooHooMan Lisen, the arrival of Socians, the great savior of the world, has been foretold as: "Marvelous signs shall appear in the sky as signs of the arrival of the savior and some angels will carry his messages from the east and the west to the whole world."</p> <p>The ancient Iranians believed so strongly in the arrival of the "Socians" that when their empire was defeated decisively in the "Qadesieh war", the third Yazdgerd turned to his great castle, "Mada'in", and said "Bless you; I will leave now and shall return with one of my descendants who has not reappeared yet" (Book of Jamasb, pages 121-122)</p> <p>However, the Shiites believe Imam Mahdi is one of the descendants of Yazdgerd's daughter. She was the wife of the third Imam of Shiites, Imam Hussein, who was the ninth forefather of Imam Mahdi.</p>
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Table 3

4.2. Books And References Regarding The Hidden Imam (Imam Mahdi)

Imam Mahdi is an undeniable reality who has been mentioned in all the divine Holy Books from eternity to the end of the world, and all divine and impious religions believe in Him and His appearance [54]. In an essay, you will find explanations about 42 collections and books of Sunni writers and scholars who have published independent books in Arabic on Imam Mahdi [55]. In some historical scriptures from the second century after Islam and after, there is a hadith narrated by Nafe' who was a narrator and a servant of Abdullah bin Omar. It contains a startling quote from Omar bin Khattab, the second Muslim Caliph: In addition to his other two characteristics, Imam Mahdi is considered a descendant of this Caliph. This hadith led to many misunderstandings and failed attempts to find the true Imam Mahdi during these first two centuries of Muslim history [42]. An essay has been prepared using the precious book of the eminent contemporary writer and bibliographer, the late Ayatollah TabaTabaei, entitled "The Prophet's household in Arabic Literature." [43]. Allamah Ashtiyani corrected Imam Mahdi's

ancestor identified in extant copies of Ibn 'Arabi. He writes: He is one of the descendants of the Prophet Muhammad and one of the descendants of Fatima. His name is like that of the prophet Muhammad and his ancestor is Husayn Ibn 'Ali Ibn Abi Talib (Maleki 1388, 60; Torabian Torqabah 1381, 203) [37]. Henry Corbin, influenced by thinkers such as Heidegger and Suhrawardi, comes with a hermeneutical view of the world. He trusts Suhrawardi's opinions. In this approach a unique ability is discovered, the basis of which resides in Malakut and the world Exemplar, the world in which Carbon finds the position of the Hidden Imam [50]. Image and illustration can play an important role in presenting the teachings of Mahdavi to the peoples of the world [44].

Figure 11

The Holy Prophet (sawa) said, "Ali Ibne Abi Talib (as) is the Imam of my Ummah and my caliph on it after me. And from his progeny is the awaited Mahdi who will fill the earth with justice and equity as it would be fraught with injustice and tyranny. By the One who has sent me with truth, as the giver of glad tidings and a warner, those who will be steadfast in faith upon him during his occultation will be more precious than red sulphur. Jabir Ibne Abdullah Ansari stood up and asked: O Messenger of Allah, is there occultation for the Qaem from your progeny? He replied: Yes, by my Lord, through him will Allah exalt those who believe and destroy those who disbelieve. O Jabir, it is one of the celestial matters and one of the secrets of Allah which is concealed from the people. Thus one who doubts in it, he in fact doubts in the matter of Allah, the Mighty and Sublime." (Kamaluddin volume 1, chapter 25, tradition 7, English)

Figure 12

The background and future history of Christians and Islam are different, but some common points can be found in this area. An important one is the confrontation with the establishment of a corrective justice-oriented government [81]. There are traditions and attitudes about the world after the death of Imam Mahdi. Some pointed to the fifty years of chaos, others referred to the occurrence of the resurrection, others stated the continuation of the government by the followers of Imam Mahdi, and the others spoke of the return of the holy imams [38]. Some people believe that Imam Mahdi will abolish the religion of Islam when he appears and replace it with a new religious law based on certain traditions. Some of these traditions are not recognized at all by Shia scholars [92]. The article presents the hadiths received from Imam Mahdi as well as 40 hadiths from Imam Ali to the Mahdi on Sunni hadiths and on the 12 topics [97]. Imam Mahdi will form a just government in the world like his ancestors. Imam Mahdi will first invite people to the legal path in a good and merciful manner with logical reasons and convincing arguments so that no one will have an excuse. Then he will not only fight arrogant oppressors and enemies of any religion, but, unlike the Prophet Muhammad, he will not compromise with the hypocrites and destroy them so that he can form a government full of justice [98].

5. Conclusion

In this article, we have discussed that Imam Mahdi has also been mentioned in other religions and, in fact, he has been mentioned in all books of other religions. The Mahdi is one of the sure

promises of God. We have proved that not only Imam Mahdi is mentioned in Quran and Islam, but also in other religions and books. In fact, in Islam, both Sunni and Shia predicted Imam Mahdi. If the Shiites, may Allah help them in His obedience, had fulfilled their covenant with united hearts, then there would have been no delay in meeting the Promised Saviour. Besides, we spoke about Holy Fatima and her characteristics. We hope this article will take an important step in acquainting people with Imam Mahdi and Jesus Christ and paving the ground for their reappearance.

Limitations

It is important to recognize the limitations of this study. Although careful research has been done to gather data, other relevant and important studies may have been overlooked. Finally, it is important that the review was limited to English and Persian studies. There are likely many other relevant studies in other languages that have not been reviewed in this study.

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7. Abbreviations :

A.T.F.S: An abbreviation of ‘Ajjil Allaahu Ta’ala Farajahu Shareef’, that is “May Allah Hasten His Reappearance”.

Amirul Momineen: Leader of the believers. Title of Imam Ali bin Abi Talib (a.s.)

Ayat: Verse of the Holy Quran

Bada: Change in divine will

Dua: Invocation

Insha-Allah: If Allah (SwT) wills

Qaim (Qaem): One would rise. A title of Imam Mahdi (a.s.)

Salawat: Allaahumma Salle alaa Muhaammadinw wa aali Muhammad

Sayyidush Shohada: Chief of the Martyrs, a title of Imam Husain (a.s.)

Surah: Chapter of Quran

Ziyarat: Visitation or recitation of salutation while facing the tomb of religious personalities

8. References:

1. Pahlevan, M., & Mahdavi Rad, M., & Rouhani Mashhadi, F. (2013). The Similarities Between Imam Mahdi And The Divine Prophets In The Holy Quran. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 7(25), 81-104. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=494936>
2. Ayati, N. (2013). The Functions Of The Symptoms And Signs Of Appearance. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 6(24), 5-23. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=316298>
3. Fahimi Esfahan, S., Habibi Tabar, H., Poodineh, M. (2018). A Critical Survey of the Entry of Mahdi in Encyclopedia Britannica, with an Emphasis on Sunni Sources. *The Promised East*, 12(45), 479-512.
4. Salimian, K. (2014). Analysis Of The Theory Of Imam Mahdi's Martyrdom From Traditions' Perspective. *Entizar E Moud*, 13(43), 49-67. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=419902>
5. Mir Damadi, S. (2015). The Prohibition Or Permit To Name Mahdi By The Title "muhammad" (reviewing The Views F Hakim Mir Damad Sheikh Horr Amely). *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 8(32), 73-86. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=436300>
6. Ayati, N. (2010). A Reflection On Some Dubious Objections On Mahdism. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 3(12), 53-77. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=183284>
7. MAAREF, M., & Kazemtouri, S. (2021). Hadith Writings in Shia Imams Traditions and Role of Ali ibn Mahziyar in their Preservation and Transferring. *HADITH STUDIES*, 13(25), 55-74. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=832116>
8. Daeinezhad, S. (2008). Intellectual Criteria: Philosophical, Dialectical, Rational And Traditions Of Mahdism. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 2(7), 81-88. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=177380>
9. Nazarpour, H. (2020). Investigating Ibn Barrajan' s Prediction of the Time of the Conquest of Jerusalem. *HISTORY OF ISLAM & IRAN*, 29(44 (134)), 145-163. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=800875>

10. Sukdaven, M. & Ahmed, S., 2017, 'Is Dhul Qarnayn, Alexander the Great? Reflecting on Muhammad Rāghib al-Ṭabbākh's contribution on a translated manuscript discovered in Timbuktu on Dul Qarnayn', *Verbum et Ecclesia* 38(1), a1696.
<https://DOI.org/10.4102/ve.v38i1.1696>
11. Fatkhullah, Faiz & Nur, Tajudin & Hidayat, I. & Darsa, Undang. (2019). Gog and Magog (Yakjuj wa Makjuj) Stories in Sundanese Manuscripts. *OKARA: Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra*. 13. 17. 10.19105/ojbs.v13i1.2233
12. Idris, Asmady & Kurtbağ, Ömer. (2019). A Comparative Study of Government Policy in Dealing with Deviant Teachings in Islam: The Case of Malaysia and Turkey. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 9. 10.6007/IJARBSS/v9-i5/5872
13. Keramati (Iran), D. (2019). Religious Education in Cyberspace: Opportunities and Threats. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of PURE LIFE (IMJPL)*, 6(17), 33-54. doi: 025/p-1.2019.2538
14. Kashfi (Iran), Z., Shafaroudi (Iran), R. (2019). Possibility of Evaluating the Level of Religious Promotion in Virtual Education. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of PURE LIFE (IMJPL)*, 6(17), 55-69. doi: 025/p-1.2019.2539
15. Zeinalipoor (Iran), F. (2019). The Impact of Cyberspace on Family and Youth (Injuries and Solutions). *International Multidisciplinary Journal of PURE LIFE (IMJPL)*, 6(17), 71-84. doi: 025/p-1.2019.2540
16. Rabbanie Golpayeganie, A. (2016). Reviewing And Criticizing Imam Mahdi's Genealogy From The Sunni's View. *Entizar E Moud*, 16(52), 6-20.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=535705>
17. Rouhani Mashhadi, F. (2014). Varieties Of Mentions Of Imam Mahdi In Quran And Explanatory Traditions. *Entizar E Moud*, 13(43), 7-28.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=419904>
18. Hasani, S. (2018). Admission areas of Imam Mahdi's birth (AS) by some Sunni Schaller's. *The Promised East*, 12(45), 207-228.
19. Maleki, A. (2019). The Relationship between Religion and Politics from the Viewpoint of Shia Imamieh with Emphasis on the Doctrine of Mahdism and From the Perspective of the Qur'an and Narrations. *Quranic Knowledge Research*, 10(37), 141-168. doi: 10.22054/rjqk.2019.38389.1842
20. Elahinejad, H., Shahrokhi, S. (2018). The Role of Mahdaviyat in the Unity and Convergence of the Islamic World. *The Promised East*, 12(47), 133-156.

21. Hashemi, S. (2017). Shiite Faced with the Emergence of the Messiah. *The Promised East*, 11(42), 87-104.
22. Rahman, Mohammad Mushfequr. (2021). *The Twelve Imams of Islam: Successor of Prophet Muhammad* PBUH
23. Alebouyeh, G., & Ayati, N. (2016). Revisiting The Narratives Of The Prophet Mohammad (pbuh) About His Successors And Explaining It In The Exclusive Number Of Twelve. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 10(37), 145-165. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=501705>
24. Maleki Rad, M. (2021). The terminology of Mahdism in Sunni sources. *JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT*, 3(1 (5)), 67-89. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=846567>
25. Musavi Keramati, S. (2019). Stating the Issue of Mahdiism in Imam Sā deqi's Approach based on the Book of Alghaybah Na'mā ni. *SIREH PAZHOUHI AHL E BEYT*, 5(8), 59-74. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=760178>
26. Ganjvar, M., & Azizi, H. (2018). Religious Normative Pluralism In Imam Mahdi's Mode Of Conduct: Imam Mahdi's Pattern Of Behavior With Followers Of Other Religions. *Comparative Theology*, 9(19), 1-4. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=604452>
27. Khosro Panah, A., & Zareie, M. (2016). A Critical Analysis On The Weakness Of The Documentation Of Hadithes Related To The Imam Mahdi's Judgment Based On The Inner State Of The Subject. *Entizar E Moud*, 16(52), 21-43. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=535708>
28. Rouhani Mashhadi, F., & Pahlevan, M., & Mahdavidrad, M. (2014). The Allusion Of Quranic Stories To Imam Mahdi And His Characteristics. *Pajuhesh-ha-ye Quran Va Hadis (iranian Journal For The Quranic Sciences & Tradition) (maqalat Wa Barrasiha)*, 46(2), 59-81. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=503144>
29. Fallah Ali Abad, M., & Reza Nezhad, A., & Heidari Charati, H. (2013). Analysis Of The Narratives Of The Age Of Imam Mahdi (a.s) (with Emphasis On Criticizing Baha'i Claim). *Entizar E Moud*, 12(39), 29-59. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=377763>
30. Salimian, K. (2013). An Analysis From The Point Of View Of Hadith Studies Regarding The Naming Mohammed For Mahdi. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 7(25), 169-188. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=494945>
31. Hosseini, S., & Taghizadeh Davari, M. (2017). Qualitative Analysis of Theories in the Process of Realizing Social Maturity in the Age of Advent. *ANDISHE-E-NOVIN-E-DINI*, 13(50), 21-44. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=697513>

32. Ghanavi, A. (2016). Messianic Ideas In The Words Of The Infallible Imam Kazem And Imam Reza. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 10(37), 5-30.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=501698>
33. Shakeri Zavardehi, R., doostmohammadi, M., Khadem Hazrati, S. (2021). Typology of the Origins of the Emergence of Approach of Denying Mahdism in Sunnis. *Entizar-e-Moud*, 20(71), 25-50.
34. Kalbasi, M., Moayedi, A. (2020). A Study on the Proof of Life of Imam Mahdi (A.S) in the Light of the Verses of Deeds Witnesses. *Entizar-e-Moud*, 20(70), 5-32.
35. Yosefian, M., Barari, M. (2020). A Study and Critique of the Traditions Claiming the Appearance of Imam Mahdi (A.S) in the years of 70 and 140 AH. *Entizar-e-Moud*, 20(70), 89-114.
36. Rad, A., azizi, S. (2020). Analysis of Mahdism Discourse, in the Hadiths of Hassan Ibn Mahboub. *Entizar-e-Moud*, 20(70), 33-58.
37. Kazemzadeh, P., Davarnia, M. (2014). The Sealness of the Wilayah of al-Mahdi and the Specification of His Ancestors according to ibn Arabi and Some Commentators of Futuhat al-makkiyyah. *Religious Inquiries*, 3(5), 63-81.
38. Shahbaziyan, M., Rezanezhad, E. (2017). Reviewing the Traditions about the World after Imam Mahdi (P.B.U.H) from Shia's Perspective. *The Promised East*, 11(42), 149-168.
39. Saeedyan Jazi, M. (2017). The Issue of Mahdism, Especially with the Approach to the News of Imam Ali ibn Abi Talib (AS). *Seraje Monir*, 8(28), 133-170. doi: 10.22054/ajsm.2019.16280.1211
40. Hashemi, S. (2018). Study of the possibility of the Mahdavi ideal of the Holy Quran. *The Promised East*, 12(45), 327-334.
41. Ramin, F., Kitouni, A. (2018). Evaluation of Zaidi's sectarian doubts about promised Mehdi according to Sheikh Sadukh. *The Promised East*, 12(45), 229-246.
42. Rastegar, P. (2010). Reread The Document And Hadith Text About The Generation Imam Mahdi. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 4(13), 107-117.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=195636>
43. Tabatabaei Yazdi, S. (2006). Bibliography The Books And Literature Made By The Sunni Scholars And Writers, About Imam Mahdi (p.b.u.h). *Safineh*, 3(10 (special Issue On The Mahdism)), 31-68. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=196185>

44. Sattari Sarbangholi, H., Kazempour, M. (2019). Rereading the illustration facilities of Hazrat Mahdi (pbuh) based on the illustration of the Imams (as) in the Islamic art of Iran. *Age of the future*, 12(30), 33-68.
45. Akbarnezhad, M. (2010). Criticism Of Ibn Taymiyya's View Concerning Imam Mahdi (p.b.u.h). *Pajuhesh-ha-ye Quran Va Hadis (iranian Journal For The Quranic Sciences & Tradition) (maqalat Wa Barrasiha)*, 42(1), 25-42.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=206113>
46. Ghanavi, A. (2014). The Development Of The Messianic Thought By Imam Sadegh (peace Be Upon Him). *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 8(29), 5-24.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=435979>
47. Ghanavi, A. (2014). Putting Forward The Mahdism Doctrine By Imam Baqir. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 7(28), 5-22. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=368810>
48. Zeinali, Q.(2020). Ibn Mas'ud Hadith and the Twelve Imams. *The Promised East*, 14(53), 9-44.
49. Ahmadi Kachayi, M., Mirzaei, A. (2020). Survey Uthman ibn Sa'id al-Amri role in the events of Imam Hassan Askari (as) and Imam Mahdi (aj) period. *The Promised East*, 14(55), 131-146.
50. Ahmadi, M. (2016). Phenomenological Analysis Of Henry Corbin Views In Discussions On Imamate And Absence Period Of Promised Imam Based On Suhrawardi's Thoughts. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 10(37), 75-95. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=501702>
51. Ghane, A. (2015). The Rule Of Friday Prayer Through Verses Of The Quran And Traditions Of Infallibles. *Quranic & Hadith Studies*, 8(2 (16)), 187-219.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=602990>
52. Zeinali, G. (2021). Analysis of the hadith *أبي اسم أبيه اسم و اسمي اسمه*: "His name is my name and his father's name is my father's name". *Mahdavi Research*, 10(37), 35-54
53. Dezhabad, H. (2012). A Review Of Ahl Al Sunnah's Reasoning About The Verse Of 'estekhlaf' And Its Relationship With The Age Of Appearance. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 6(22), 53-90.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=287351>
54. Anvar, S. (2000). Imam Mahdi (a.s). *Journal Of The Faculty Of Letters And Humanities (tehran)*, 41-42(153-154), 371-383. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=29179>
55. Tabatabaei Yazdi, S. (2006). Bibliography Of The Selected Books And Literature Made By The Sunni Scholars And Writers, About Imam Al- Mahdi (p.b.u.h): The Unknown, And Not Available Manuscripts. *Safineh*, 3(11 (special Issue On The Mahdism)), 77-88.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=196252>

56. Salimian, K. (2018). The Study of the Effect of Sunni Traditions from the sources of the people of the Book In the category of security during the advent of Imam Mahdi (pbuh). *The Promised East*, 12(45), 59-78.
57. Tajmiralli, F. (2013). The Wise Women (in Islamic Early Centuries). *Woman And Culture*, 4(14), 109-118. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=336329>
58. Ghahremani, B. (2015). The Life Style Of Fatimah (pbuh) As A Model For Religious Life Style. *The Socio Cultural Strategy Journal*, 4(15), 219-241. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=510283>
59. Saeidi, S. (2018). Woman Of Kindness, Fatimah Bint Muhammad In Lamentations Of Minab. *Ourmazd Journal*, -(1 (42)), 25-38. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=603814>
60. Nemati Pir Ali, D. (2008). The Political Behavior Of Fatimah (pbuh) As A Perfect Man. *Women's Strategic Studies (ketabe Zanan)*, 10(39), 7-34. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=117107>
61. Rostami, M., & Shadkam, H. (2011). Hazrat-e Fatima Zahra (a.s.), A Model Of Spiritual Insight In Velayaymadary. *Minhaj*, 7(12), 147-173. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=197970>
62. Mir Baqeri, S. (2011). Appellations From The Holy Quran About Hazrat-e Zahra (a.s.) (relying On Kosar Surah). *Minhaj*, 7(12), 111-123. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=197963>
63. Gharavi Naeini, N. (2010). Hazrate Zahra's (s.a.) Bound With The Quran. *Minhaj*, 6(10), 7-21. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=185092>
64. Mirzaee Qalam Khani, M., & Gharavi Naeeni, N. (2011). Fatima (a.s.), A Blessing From God. *Minhaj*, 7(12), 87-109. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=197960>
65. Maaref, M. (2011). Criteria Of Faith In Hazrat-e Fatima's (a.s.) Pattern Of Thought And Behavior. *Minhaj*, 7(12), 9-29. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=197952>
66. Tabibi, M. (2011). A Review Of Hazrat-e Zahra's (a.s.) Life Style In Defending Velayat. *Minhaj*, 7(12), 175-192. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=197973>
67. Bahari, H., & Ameli, S. (2017). Fadak In The Mirror Of Islamic Jurisprudence. *Feqh Va Mabani-ye Hoquq-e Eslami (iranian Journal For Jurisprudence & Essentials Of The Islamic Law) (maqalat Wa Barrasiha)*, 49(2) , 231-246. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=579410>

68. Meghyasi, H., & Farahani, S. (2015). Foregrounding In Fatimah's Sermon Of Fadak. *Hadith Studies*, 7(13), 33-56. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=481119>
69. Moradi Kiasaraii, S., & Mofatteh, M. (2019). A Comparative Study on “ the Prophets’ Inheritance” and “ the Sermon of Fatimah Zahra (PBUH) for the Expropriation of Fadak” According to the Views of Yusuf She’ ar and Sunni and Shi’ ite Commentators. *JOURNAL OF COMPARATIVE TAFSIR STUDIES*, 4(1 (9)), 323-374. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=777778>
70. Eizadi, M., & Faghih Imani, M. (2014). Review And Analysis Of The Narratives Of Origin Nickname “abu Traub”. *Quranic & Hadith Studies*, 7(2 (14)), 173-202. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=602888>
71. KARIMI, Z., & mahdipour, z. (2021). Proper Nutrition in Imam Ali's (A. S) Conduct. *SIREH PAZHOUHI AHL E BEYT*, 6(11), 23-35. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=791735>
72. Mousavi, S., & Morsalpour, M., & Zeini Malekabad, h. (2020). Imam Ali's Ruling Methods against Social Inequalities. *SIREH PAZHOUHI AHL E BEYT*, 5(9), 29-44. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=760216>
73. Hajizadeh, Y. (2021). Imam Ali (AS) spiritual life in choosing food and clothing. *SIREH PAZHOUHI AHL E BEYT*, 7(12), 19-32. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=848557>
74. Hosseinpour, S., & Jabbari, M. (2013). History And The Sequence Of Events Which Ended In Presence Zahra' (a) Martyrdom. *Tarikh Dr Ayene Ye Pazhohesh*, 10(2), 0-0. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=444528>
75. Musavi, s. (2020). Ibn Babaway, Shiite writin, Hazrat Fatima. *JOURNAL OF HISTORICAL APPROACHES TO QURAN AND HADITH STUDIES*, 25(66), 11-22. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=735511>
76. Atarzadeh, M. (2008). Fatimah Al-zahra (pbuh): An Example Of Muslim Women’s Socio-political Participation. *Women's Strategic Studies (ketabe Zanan)*, 10(39), 99-126. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=117112>
77. Hajianpour, H., & Karimi, Z. (2016). Medical Presence Of Women In Battles Of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). *Journal Of Medical Ethics And History Of Medicine*, 8(6), 22-33. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=507895>
78. Sadqinya, M., & Kazemirad, R. (2013). The Belief In The Coming Of The Promised Saviour And Creation Of New Sects In Islam And Christianity (the Last Two Centuries). *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 7(27), 83-106. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=354073>

79. Abdipour, H., Mohammadi, M. (2018). End Time and Its Political-Social Implications in Abrahamic Religions with a Common Approach. *The Promised East*, 12(47), 227-246.
80. Arab, M. (2014). The Promised Savior in Pre-Islamic Great Religions. *Comparative Theology*, 5(11), 149-168.
81. Emami Jomeh, M., & Jahan Ahmadi, A. (2010). Comparative Studies In Islamic Antichrist Theology And Christian. *Comparative Theology*, 1(3), 19-32.
<https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=200756>
82. Allamah Sayyed Muhammad Husayn Tabatabai, Translated and Edited by Seyyed Hossein Nasr. 1975. *SHI'ITE ISLAM*. State University of New York Press
83. Shaker, Muhammad K. (2005) *Spirituality and prayer in Shiite Islam*. AHRC. ISBN 9780906165553
84. Haqqy, Ahmad. (2020). The Concept of The Mahdi Priest by Shiah. *MAGHZA: Jurnal Ilmu Al-Qur'an dan Tafsir*. 5. 87-105. 10.24090/maghza.v5i1.4044.
85. Rubin, U. (1997). Apocalypse and authority in Islamic Tradition: the emergence of the Twelve Leaders. *Al-Qanṭara*, 18(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.3989/alqantara.1997.v18.i1.514>
86. Klemm, Verena, "Fāṭima bt. Muḥammad", in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, THREE, Edited by: Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John Nawas, Everett Rowson. Consulted online on 26 February 2022 http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_ei3_COM_27039
87. NURU MOHAMMED. SEPTEMBER 2016. CONCEPT OF MAHDI IN EARLY SHIA.
88. Maleki, A. (2021). A comparative comparison of the idea of government neutrality in liberalism and Islam (focusing on the teachings of Mahdism and with a Quranic and narrative approach). *Mahdavi Research*, 10(37), 77-96.
89. Rabbani Golpayegani, A. (2021). An Analysis on the Political and Ideological Rule of Islam in the Age of Appearance. *Entizar-e-Moud*, 20 (71), 5-24.
90. Mīrī, S.S., Sa'ādatniya, R., & Fakhkhārī, A. (2020). The Meaning of Sabab as the Reason for the Victoriousness of Dhul-Qarnayn
91. Ghazikhani, H. (2009). The Historical Approval Of The Of Existence Of Imam Of The Time (mahdi) Using The Method Of Reviewing The Post Of Representative In The Era Of Short Absence Fakeness Of The Governor Post, Rejecting The Doubts Or Ambiguities Raised By Ahmad Katib About The Denial Of Existence Of Imam Of The Time. *Mashreq-e Mouood*, 3(9), 81-94. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=199439>

92. Ayati, N. (2008). Imam Mahdi (pbuh), The Reviver Of The Religious Law (2). Mashreq-e Mouood, 1(5), 9-34. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=195879>
93. Tarkhan, G. (2020). The Health of Imam of the Time (A.S) and the Possibility of Measuring the Effect of Prayer on its Realization. Entizar-e-Moud, 20(69), 29-51.
94. Ohadi Haeri, P. (2008). Geographical Range Of Shiite Resident Areas And Its Impact On Flourishing Theology, Jurisprudence And Traditions And Sayings During The Absence Of Short Duration. Journal Of Geographical Sciences, 7(10), 89-106. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=214264>
95. Sadeghi Kashani, M. (2012). Rabiol Avval, The Ninth: The Day Of Mahdism And Imamate Morning. Mashreq-e Mouood, 6(22), 41-51. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=287344>
96. Esmaceli, E. (2008). A Caravan Of Qommiss To The City Of Samerra And Their Visiting Imam Mahdi (pbuh). Mashreq-e Mouood, 2(7), 117-130. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=177412>
97. Ahdullahi, a. (2001). Mahdi In Imam Ali's Discourse. Journal Of Language And Literature Faculty Of Letters And Humanities (journal Of Faculty Of Letters And Humanities (language And Literature)), 33(3-4), 553-570. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=39695>
98. Rahimi Sabet, S. (2020). The Conduct of Prophet Muhammad (s) and Imam Mahdi (a) When Encountering the Opponent: Comparative Study. Mahdavi Research, 9(33), 125-144.